

EFFECT OF OFFSHORE ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITIONS ON THE MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF GLASS FIBER REINFORCED POLYMERS (GFRPs)

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ABSTRACT

This work investigates the effect of temperature and salt water ageing on the mechanical behavior of a glass fiber-reinforced polymers (GFRP). Tensile, in-plane shear and interlaminar shear tests were carried out using a digital image correlation (DIC) system. Specimens were tested at room conditions (21 °C), -10 °C and 70 °C. In addition, specimens were placed for ageing in a 3.5% weight salt water solution to simulate the long-term degradation of the material in the sea. An ageing process was also performed in high temperature to accelerate the material degradation.

KEYWORDS

GFRP; tensile; in-plane shear; interlaminar shear; temperature; ageing

INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced polymers (FRPs) have become increasingly popular in structural applications due to their design flexibility and excellent mechanical properties. In this sense, wrapped composite joints have emerged as a promising alternative to conventional welded joints in steel circular hollow sections for structures placed in the sea (Feng et al., 2022). These structures are manufactured as laminated shells where the fibers withstand high tensile and shear loadings.

The design of composite structures for offshore applications must consider not only the loading scenarios but also the effects of environmental conditions. Changes of temperature have shown significant impact on the performance of composite materials (Manalo et al., 2017), leading to increased failure risks. In the case of immersion in seawater, moisture diffuses into the material and lead to fiber–matrix interface debonding due to the difference in moisture expansion rate (Sheng et al, 2021). Understanding the effects of temperature and moisture on fiber reinforced polymers (FRPs) is crucial for ensuring structural integrity and reliable operation of composite structures in various environmental conditions.

This work investigates the effect of temperature and salt water ageing on the mechanical behavior of a glass fiber-reinforced polymers (GFRP). Tensile, in-plane shear (IPS) and interlaminar shear (ILS) tests were carried out. Specimens were tested at room conditions (21 °C), -10 °C and 70 °C to evaluate the range of operational temperatures. In addition, specimens were placed for ageing in a salt water solution to simulate the long-term degradation of the material in the offshore environment. An ageing process was also carried out in high temperature to accelerate the material degradation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Specimen manufacture

Glass fiber reinforced polymer (GFRP) plates were manufactured. A hand lay-up lamination was performed using a modified vinyl ester resin and glass fiber plies. Each ply of composite is made of a layer of bi-directional woven stucked to a layer of chopped strand mat. The plates were allowed to cure in air conditions of 18 ± 1 °C and $50\pm 5\%$ relative humidity. Then, plates were cut to coupon specimens using water jet. In order to complete the polymerization of the resin, part of the specimens were post cured in an oven at 120 °C for 1 h per 1 mm thickness. The post cured composite material has a glass transition temperature (T_g) of 120 °C.

The composite tensile specimens were designed in accordance with ISO 527 type 4 geometry using 2 mirrored 0/90° plies with the woven as outer surface. The nominal length of the specimens is 300

mm, and the average width and thickness of 24.90 ± 0.24 mm and 2.58 ± 0.12 mm, respectively, were measured using a digital caliper at the measurement region.

The composite IPS specimens were designed in accordance with ISO 14129 using 2 mirrored $\pm 45^\circ$ plies with the woven as outer surface. The nominal length of the specimens is 250 mm, and the average width and thickness of 24.74 ± 0.20 mm and 2.43 ± 0.08 mm, respectively, were measured using a digital caliper from 3 different sections of each specimen.

The composite IPS specimens were designed in accordance with ISO 19927 double beam shear test using 6 plies stacked in the same direction. The average length, width and thickness of 114.39 ± 0.46 , 37.67 ± 0.06 and 6.91 ± 0.27 mm, respectively, were measured using a digital caliper.

Ageing process

Specimens were placed for ageing in a solution of 3.5% weight of salt mixed to demineralized water to simulate the sea water environment. The water parameters of temperature, conductivity and pH were measured during the ageing process, as shown in Figure 1. Nearly constant temperatures of 23 ± 0.5 °C and 69.8 ± 1.1 °C, and conductivities of 53.8 ± 0.1 and 55.5 ± 0.5 were measured from the room temperature (RT) and high temperature (HT) tanks, respectively. The initial pH is moderately alkaline immediately after the preparation of the solution and then stabilizes around neutral values in both tanks. Average parameters of sea water may varies significantly according to the sea, distance from the shore and depth. The mesured parameters are a reasonable representation of sea water environment.

Figure 1: Measured parameters of the salt water solution

Testing method

Tests were performed using an universal testing machine coupled with a 100 kN load cell. Figure 2 shows the experimental set up of tensile, IPS and ILS tests. Sandpaper was used as tabs in the tensile and IPS tests to improve the distribution of the gripping pressure. The ILS tests were performed using a 5-point bending test fixture. During the tests, a constant crosshead opening displacement of 1 mm/min. was applied. Displacement and load data points are taken every 0.5 s.

A climate chamber was used in the set up for the tests at -10 °C and 70 °C. These temperature range covers the minimum and maximum operational conditions. Specimens were maintained in a constant temperature for 4 hours before the tests, in the case of tensile and IPS test specimens, and for 7 hours, in the case of ILSS test specimens, for ensuring stabilization of the temperature field in the specimens. Table 2 shows the test matrix. A total of 5 valid test results were performed for each configuration.

Figure 2: Experimental set up of (a) tensile, (b) IPS and (c) ILS tests

Table 1: Test matrix

Test type	Code	Post curing	Ageing condition	Test Temperature (°C)	Number of Tests
Tensile / In-plane shear / Interlaminar shear	NPC	No	-	21 ±1	5
	PC	120 °C	-	21 ±1	5
	LT	120 °C	-	-10 ±1	5
	HT	120 °C	-	70 ±1	5
	RTA	120 °C	salt water 23 °C	21 ±1	5
	HTA	120 °C	salt water 70 °C	21 ±1	5

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Moisture uptake

The moisture absorption was measured and wet specimens were tested. The weight uptake of representative specimens aged in salt water at room temperature are shown in Figure 3. Saturation is more clearly observed in the IPS specimen, which has the smallest dimensions, at 0.5% moisture uptake. Figure 4 shows the weight uptake from specimens aged in high temperature (70 °C). In this condition, the moisture equilibrium is reached in significant lower time.

Figure 3: Moisture diffusion measurements of specimens immersed in room temperature (23 °C)

Figure 4: Moisture diffusion measurements of specimens immersed in high temperature (70 °C)

Tensile behavior

The tensile strength of the composite material is obtained by the maximum load measured from the test divided by the initial cross section area of the specimen at the failure section. The average of 5 tensile test results is presented in Figure 5 for each configuration. Non-post cured and post cured specimens tested at room temperature (21 °C) presented similar behavior. Then, increases of 11.8% and 4.4% of the tensile strength are noticed in tests at -10 °C and 70 °C. In the aged samples, a slight reduction of 2.8% of the tensile strength is perceived after ageing in room temperature (23 °C) for 121 days. Lastly, specimens aged in in 70 °C presented a severe reduction of 55.6% after 106 days of immersion.

Figure 5: Summary of tensile strength

In-plane shear (IPS) behavior

The IPS strength of the composite material is obtained by the maximum load measured from the test divided by the initial cross section area of the specimen. The average of 5 IPS test results are presented in Figure 6 for the post curing and temperature analysis, and in Figure 7. Post cured specimens tested at room temperature (21 °C) presented a slight increase of 4.2% of the IPS strength compared to non-post cured samples. Then, the IPS strength increased 7.6% in tests at -10 °C, and and remained similar in tests at 70 °C. In the aged samples, a slight reduction of 3.2% of the tensile strength is perceived after ageing in room temperature (23 °C) for 106 days. Specimens aged in in 70 °C presented a severe reduction of 47.0% after 106 days of immersion.

Figure 6: Summary of IPS strength

Interlaminar shear (ILS) behavior

The ILS strength of the composite material is obtained by the maximum load measured from the test divided by the initial cross section area of the specimen. The average of 5 ILS test results is presented in Figure 7 for each configuration. Post cured specimens tested at room temperature (21 °C) presented a slight reduction of 5.2% in the ILS strength compared to non-post cured samples. Tests performed in low temperature (-10 °C) presented no change, while high temperature (70 °C) showed a significant decrease of 16.6% in the ILS strength. Changes in the flexural modulus are also noticed in the material at 70 °C, as showed in the load-displacement curves from Figure 8. In the case of aged samples, a slight reduction of 7.2% of the ILS strength is perceived after ageing in room temperature

(23 °C) for 112 days. Finally, specimens aged in in 70 °C presented a significant reduction of 38.6% after 97 days of immersion.

Figure 7: Summary of ILS strength

Figure 8: Representative load-displacement curves of the ILS tests in different temperature conditions

Finally, a summary of the mechanical properties obtained from each specimen conditions is presented in Table 2. Overall, changes of temperature showed slight variations of the strength of the composite material, as well as the moisture degradation for the tested ageing time. However, ageing in high temperature resulted in severe degradation of the material properties in a similar timespan. The significance (p-value) of the test results is shown for each specimen condition compared to the reference post cured specimens tested in room conditions.

Table 2: Summary of mechanical properties

Test Type	Parameter	Specimen Condition					
		NPC	PC	LT	HT	RTA	HTA
Tensile tests	Tensile strength (MPa)	196.5	196.2	219.4	204.7	190.7	87.0
	Mean deviation	12.4	16.4	10.5	7.8	7.4	12.7
	P-value	0.9776	1	0.0334	0.3356	0.5197	4.11E-06
IPS tests	IPS strength (MPa)	109.9	114.5	123.1	113.2	110.8	60.7
	Mean deviation	9.4	14.5	4.9	6.1	4.4	2.3
	P-value	0.5708	1	0.2616	0.8617	0.6110	9.70E-04
ILS tests	ILS strength (MPa)	37.27	35.31	35.20	29.45	32.77	21.69
	Mean deviation	0.17	0.89	1.01	0.78	1.08	0.40
	P-value	0.0108	1	0.8749	1.04E-05	0.0071	3.43E-07

CONCLUSION

The effect of temperature and salt water ageing on the mechanical behavior of a GFRP was investigated. Tensile, in-plane shear (IPS) and interlaminar shear (ILS) tests were carried out. Specimens were tested at room conditions (21 °C), -10 °C and 70 °C to evaluate the range of operational temperatures. Additionally, specimens were aged in a salt water solution to simulate the long-term degradation of the material in the offshore environment. An ageing process was also carried out in high temperature to accelerate the material degradation.

Post curing showed increase the IPS strength and decrease the ILS strength, while did not affect the tensile strength, which is a property less sensitive to matrix changes.

Tensile and IPS strength increased in low temperature (LT) while did not have significant change in high temperature (HT). However, the ILS strength decreased significantly in LT as the matrix presents a more brittle behavior.

The period of around 4 months of ageing at 23 °C caused a slight reduction of the composite material properties. The IPS strength was the most affected, which was also the earliest specimen to reach moisture equilibrium.

The ageing process at 70 °C accelerated the moisture diffusion process and caused severe degradation of the mechanical properties of the composite material in both fiber and matrix dominated properties. Mechanical properties obtained from material tests in different temperatures and after ageing are fundamental for the optimization of design and prediction of the performance of the structure in operational conditions.

CITATIONS

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.